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Work life balance -----Case study of Tata consultancy service

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Abstract

Every company wants to succeed in capturing the market and maximizing the profit. With the changes in technology and increase in globalization the world has become a village which leads to high competition and complexity in performance of work.

As companies are not only competing with domestic companies but with companies all over the world, this is when innovation and balancing work life is needed in a company. How can a company be different from others and retain workforce? Innovation can only be achieved when there are talented human resource and good H R practices in the company. Good HRM practices will lead to a balanced life of human resources.

Innovation in companies is through talented minds in the company. Company has to acquire, develop and retain these people. This paper is a case study of the Tata consultancy services TCS. Secondary data is used to identify how TCS manages to retain the best talented workforce. It also studies the various HRM practices followed by TCS to maintain Work Life Balance .The HRM practices of TCS are understood in depth and a linkage between HR practices and innovative talented employees is drawn.

Keywords: HRM Practices, Innovation, Talented employees, Case study, Work life balance, TCS

Introduction

Work life Balance brings together a number of important human resources (HR) and management initiatives. Quite often, organisations adopting a WLB approach focus on co-ordinating and integrating:

- Recruitment – ensuring that the right people are attracted to the organisation.
- Retention – developing and implementing practices that reward and support employees.
- Employee Development – ensuring continuous informal and formal learning and development.
- Leadership and ‘high potential employee’ development – specific development programs for existing and future leaders.
- Performance management – specific processes that nurture and support performance, including feedback/measurement.
- Workforce planning – planning for business and general changes, including the older workforce and current/future skills shortages.
- Culture – development of positive, progressive and high performance ‘way of operating’.

At present, the skill shortages and the ageing work force are also helping organisations to focus on the talent management and work life balance . Many leading companies have decided to develop their own people, rather than trying to hire fully skilled workers. In summary, every organisation should be implementing WLB principles and approaches.

ABOUT TATA CONSULTANCY SERVICES LTD (TCS)

Tata consultancy services (TCS), established in the year 1968, is the largest provider of Information Technology (IT) and Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) services in India. TCS is an IT services, consulting and business solutions organisation that delivers real results to global business, ensuring a level of certainty which no other firm can match. TCS offers a consulting-led, integrated portfolio of IT, BPS, infrastructure, engineering and assurance services. This is delivered through its unique Global Network Delivery Model, recognised as the benchmark of excellence in software development. A part of the Tata group, India’s largest industrial conglomerate, TCS has over 353,000 of the world’s best-trained consultants in 46 countries. The company generated consolidated revenues of US \$16.5 billion for year ended march 31, 2016 and is listed on the National Stock Exchange and Bombay Stock Exchange in India.

TCS is now placed among the ‘Big 4’ most valuable IT services brands worldwide. In 2015, TCS is ranked 64th overall in the Forbes World’s Most Innovative Companies ranking, making it both the highest-ranked IT services company and the first Indian Company. It is the world’s 10th largest IT services provider, measured by the revenues. It is ranked 10th on the

Fortune India 500 list. TCS is one of the largest private sector employers in India and the second largest employer among listed Indian companies.

TCS over years has successfully leveraged various global knowledge resources and has ensured that its workforce gets the best training and development opportunities. Today learning has become a way of life in TCS. The company has invested heavily in research and development and has played a critical role in helping develop a skilled resource pool for the technology industry. TCS has a diverse range of global CSR initiatives in the areas of education, health and environment, and over the years has successfully transformed lives through various educational and skills development programs.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To explore the development program of training as a program to initiate WLB in TCS.
- To develop a model.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Secondary sources are used for collection of information. Data are collected from earlier research work or project works, company website and through internet. The information is collected from the personnel site of the company which launched for informing people regarding the company. The company had launched a site called www.tcs.com. Even the information is collected from several sites of internet. The techniques of research had become easier through the network. Several books from famous authors about talent management are also referred. It is quite helpful to adopt new ideologies of different thinkers.

WLB MODEL OF TCS

Training and development is a continuous process. This model is developed to understand the training programs conducted by TCS aimed at the new recruits, experienced professionals, potential candidates and training also as a part of CSR activity. These training and development programs enhances the capabilities of an employee to be ready to perform possible future jobs.

Training programs for the potential candidates

Research suggest that only about 2% of all graduating science students in the country are employable, and usually lack the basic skills required to survive and progress in the technology industry. Hence TCS conducts following programs:

Open ignite

TCS through ignite program try to create a skilled resource pool for the IT industry. TCS Ignite is an intense learning program for young science graduates who join Tata Consultancy

Services. Today, TCS is the largest recruiter of fresh science graduates in the country, and each year, thousands of the best and brightest graduates join the TCS Ignite program. Candidates are selected through open learning platform, called Open Ignite. This online platform attracts over a 100,000 users from science community from across 6000 colleges across 700 towns all over the country. Selected candidates are made part of a six month, state-of-the-art learning program, where they are taught through various technology enabled learning tools that makes learning fun. Students are exposed to various real world projects, which ensure that they are job ready by the end of the program. On completion of the training, associates are deployed in TCS client projects. Out of 4000 ignite alumni, about 10% are deployed onsite and about 5% are project leaders. Several are named inventors in patent applications.

Academic Learning Collaboration

As a market leader in a knowledge economy, TCS believes in investing in early stage research to drive innovation. TCS have formed alliances with reputed academic institutions globally to encourage new developments in the area of research. The academic alliance program, a part of the TCS Co-Innovation Network results in promising ideas which stem from pure technology research and real-world scenarios.

- **Jadavpur University ME Program in Software Engineering:** this program was launched in 2004 as an area of collaboration between TCS and Jadavpur University, Kolkata, West Bengal, exemplifying an effective industry-academia relationship and has been successfully running 10 batches since then. TCS-JU jointly developed the curriculum for this program. 198 TCSers admitted since the inception.
- **IIT Madras M.Tech Program in Mechanical, Engineering Design, Aerospace and Applied Mechanics departments:** lack of courses for specialised skills in High End Engineering Design and Computational Engineering prompted TCS to collaborate with IIT Madras to start this program in 2005. TCS sponsored infrastructure for the ‘Center for Finite Element Analysis and Design (CFEAD)’ Lab. This program created talent pool and provided strong foundation in areas like Strength of Materials, Thermal Engineering, Mechanics of Solids, and High Performance Computing. 92 TCSers admitted since 2005.
- **Amrita-SUNY Twin PG Program- MBA and MS in Management of IT Services:** this collaborative program jointly offered by Amrita University and SUNY Buffalo University will fetch two Master’s degrees. One is an Executive-MBA (EMBA) degree from Amrita University in the area of General Management and other is a Master of Science (MS) in Management of IT Services from SUNY Buffalo. 39 TCSers admitted since 2011.
- **TCS Faculty Development Programs:** TCS Faculty Development Programs (FDPs) are well respected in Academia. In the Financial year 2012-2013, 276 Programs were conducted covering 10228 Faculty from 254 institutes. Few typical FDPs are:

Adopting Cloud Computing- Impact on Service Management Process, Advanced Techniques in Computational Intelligence, Analytics for intelligent Infrastructure-Signal Processing and Data Processing, Business Intelligence and Cloud Computing, High Performance Computing (HPC) and IT Infrastructure for Automobile Industry, Mobility- Introduction, Android/IOS/Windows etc.

- Curriculum Development in Engineering and Industrial Services: TCS EIS vertical designed a module ‘Foundation Skills in Integrated Product Development’ for different branches of engineering, as a part of overall curriculum revamping effort. The same is being deployed in 18 institutes across India, on pilot basis.

Training program when employees are in TCS

- **Fresher**

Aspire – An E-learning module for students

TCS Aspire is mandatory for all associates joining TCS as fresher. It is an online interactive pre-learning program for all new recruits which will help them to understand some basic concepts. The course contains 4 modules of IT Foundation skills introduction to Computers, Programming Fundamentals, Problem Solving and Databases. It also has one module on soft skills required by the IT Professionals. The module is used by 35000 fresh recruiters of TCS in the financial year 2013 for enhancing their skills. The modules are available to them in their final semester in their undergraduate program in Engineering. Since it is an E-learning module they could use it at their own pace of learning.

Initial Learning Program (ILP)

The Initial Learning Program, the strongest and the best assured grooming platform for all new recruits of TCS. The ILP aims to transform fresh engineering graduates from diverse disciplines into software professionals and to initiate them into the TCS way of life. The ILP model has continuously evolved along with the changing needs of the business. Trainees are not only introduced to various technologies, they are also provided with project delivery, project management and business or life skills. The trainees are expected to maintain a log of their daily learning, and this is periodically reviewed by their respective assessors. The trainees are required to attain a pre-defined readiness level for being deployable to projects. Remedial programs are also offered for slow learners so that they can catch up with the expectations. Everything that is learnt at ILP is a virtual learning which is the most productive way of learning to trainees.

- **Experience** – TCS has over the years introduce various continuous learning programs for its experienced professionals. This spans issues like business strategies, project needs, technology and business directions. Aside from meeting individual aspirations, it also addresses the long term, short term and medium term needs of the organisation.

Enterprise Architects (EA)

TCS learning and development team in collaboration with Technology Excellence Group has designed the EA Star program that is aimed at building Enterprise Architects. The program was created to cater to the increasing demand for Enterprise Architects, and the demand for TOGAF certified professionals in various project assignments. So far, over 700 employees have gone through the program, enabling career progression for the associates and creating strong architect community in TCS.

Ambassador Corp

TCS Ambassador Corp is a leadership development program, which prepares experienced employees for global sales roles. TCS's Ambassador Corps Programme focusses on critical business and communication skills and also equips managers to tackle challenges posed by cultural diversity. It offers an accelerated learning curve and trains managers to take their place on the global stage from the day they land in the international marketplace.

- **Leadership, Communications and Life Skills**

Ambassador Corp – this program enhances the leadership skill in an individual. It helps in developing the critical business and communication skills and also to tackle the cultural diversity challenges.

ICALMS

TCS offers iCALMS (Integrated Competency and Learning Management System)- the sole repository of all learning activity in the organisation and the one-stop-shop for all learning at TCS. It is a Competency Management tool which helps to integrate the skills set required and manpower available at a point of time. It bridges the gap between the existing competency and expected competency required for the associates. These gaps are then addressed by learning modules designed to fulfil the needs of the organisation.

- **All**

Knowledge Management

Knowledge Management is concerned with creating organisational environments for people to share, create and leverage knowledge for innovation and competitive advantage. TCS has developed a web based Enterprise wide Knowledge Management System known as **KNOWMAX**, which is available globally to all TCS consultants. This platform encompasses focus on deriving reusable assets. KNOWMAX acts as a central knowledge bank for all projects being executed by TCS and reduces cycle time. Apart from global assets in KNOWMAX which are available to all authorised users, KNOWMAX holds assets that are customer specific which can be accessed only by the project teams working for that customer. In addition to KNOWMAX, all key accounts maintain relationship specific portals that provide an effective knowledge management mechanism and repository for all relationship assets.

Books 24x7

An extensive, fully searchable web-based reference tool targeted to meet the information needs of TCS employees. It offers a variety of ready-access titles that cover a broad selection of subjects and topics.

Training as a part of CSR (inclusive growth)**TCS Maitree**

A number of non-work related employee engagement initiatives such as fun events, sports, cultural activities and volunteering for social causes are organized across the globe under its employee engagement platform known as 'Maitree'. The culture of volunteering helps employee bonding within the organization and reduces stress at work. TCS Maitree, founded in February 2002, strives to create a spirit of camaraderie among TCS associates and their families by organizing social activities and events. TCS has grown tenfold in the last few years with associates working in several locations around the world. TCS Maitree encourages associates and their families to look upon themselves as a part of TCS' extended family. The initiatives undertaken through TCS Maitree cultivate and propagate volunteer-driven, meaningful activities for associates and their families. Human Resources within TCS leads, directs and facilitates all such associate engagement activities and programmes related to Corporate Sustainability. Just off the Mumbai-Pune highway, an hour's drive from Panvel, lies in the village of Wazapur in the Raigad district of Maharashtra. The village till recently was devoid of even basic amenities. Today, however, it has witnessed a transformation largely owing to the tireless effort of hundreds of TCS volunteers working under the 'TCS-Maitree' banner. The volunteers in the last three years have helped to sustain holistic development in Wazapur based on partnerships. A sustainable model has been built to improve education, healthcare and environment in the area.

Impact through Empowerment

The guiding program of TCS's CSR program is 'Impact through Empowerment'. More than 25 women from three villages in the area were taught to perform basic calculations and were made aware of issues like health and hygiene.

Affirmative Action Program

TCS Affirmative Action endeavours to 'Improve the employability of graduates' from socially disadvantaged sections and other underprivileged categories across India who are unable to get jobs due to lack of communication skills, low confidence levels or other barriers unrelated to their educational qualifications. A powerful, imaginative and interactive training program has been devised by experienced trainers at TCS BPO which lasts for a total of 80-100 hours over a period of around 15-20 days. Apart from providing education and making youth more employable, the program also aims to provide employment opportunities to those trained in TCS BPS. More than 30000 underprivileged young graduates have been made employable under the program, since its launch in 2010.

TCS Udaan

Project 'Udaan', is a joint and novel initiative by National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) - Government of India and Special Industry Initiative (SII) to help Kashmir youth join the mainstream of corporate India. TCS has been associated with the program since its inception and aims to train and create employment opportunities for at least 850 youth from Jammu and Kashmir, over a 5 year period. The training intervention provides the youth with the requisite knowledge, skills and competencies required in the corporate world over a period of 3.5 months. The program covers the entire gamut of business skills like Business English, Presentation Skills and builds competence in domain and process areas while leveraging from innovative learning methodologies like games and movies. In addition to this, the curriculum also includes life skills and performing arts like dance, music and drama to enhance and enrich the overall personality of the participants.

CONCLUSION

Today, the concept of WLB continues to be adopted as more companies come to realize that their employees' talents and skills drive their business success. In addition to this, it has come to be established that employee retention is more cost effective than hiring. As such, in order to support its key objectives TCS has aligned talent management with business strategy, which has helped to nurture talent and retain it. The famous industrialist Andrew Carnegie of 19th century have said 'Take away my factories, my plants; take away my railroads, my ships, my transportation, take away my money; strip me of all these but leave me my key people, and in two or three years, I will have them all again'.

Effective WLB requires not only developing people for their current roles, but also getting them ready for their next transition.

The performance and career management processes of TCS are fully globalised. Digitized systems have been enhanced and new 'Career Hub' have been launched for streamlining

the process of recording aspirations, identifying high potentials, mentoring and tracking career movement of employees. The culture of reward and recognition in TCS is aided by 'TCS Gems', the global reward and recognition tool, with well-defined criteria and processes to enhance performance. TCS conducts appraisal of its regular employees twice in a year, and also at the end of the project in case of employees hired specially for various projects. In order to identify its outstanding talent, TCS has been recognising the contribution of its people in many ways. Training and development program conducted are a competitive advantage to TCS.

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